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Research Article

Exploring the Role of Technology in Enhancing Accounting Practices: AIS Adoption Among SMEs in Mauritius

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the factors influencing the intention to adopt Accounting Information Systems (AIS) among Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Mauritius, using the Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) framework and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Adopting AIS is inherently connected to technological advancements, particularly in artificial intelligence and digital innovations, which have transformative potential for professional practices. By focusing on SMEs in Mauritius, this study investigates the key drivers of AIS adoption and the readiness of these organizations to integrate such technologies into their operations. The findings contribute to the broader view of how technology shapes professional landscapes and supports organizational efficiency and growth. Data for this research were collected through surveys administered to 150 SME owners in Mauritius. The data were analyzed using SPSS V26.0 software to identify the determinants impacting AIS adoption. The results reveal that competitive pressure, perceived ease of use, perceived behavioural control, and perceived benefits significantly influence SMEs' intention to adopt AIS. However, factors such as relative advantage, perceived usefulness, firm size, and perceived risks were found to have an insignificant effect on adoption intentions. This study's findings are based on the specific context of Mauritius, which may limit the generalizability of the results to SMEs in different regions or industries. Future research could expand the sample size or use longitudinal studies to provide a more robust understanding of AIS adoption. From a practical perspective, the study offers valuable insights for policymakers and business leaders to promote AIS adoption by addressing critical factors like competitive pressure and ease of use. Increased AIS adoption can enhance operational efficiency, improve business decision-making, and foster economic growth in Mauritius. This research adds to the literature by applying the TOE and TAM frameworks in the context of AIS adoption among Mauritian SMEs.

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1. Introduction

Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are critical to an economy's overall performance. SME interest is growing in industrialised and emerging nations and nations in transition. According to Nketsiah and Durst et al. (2018), their sustained existence and expansion are vital to the economy. Numerous economies rely heavily on it, yet manual procedures might challenge financial management. For SMEs, maintaining proper financial records can be challenging. SMEs still lag in maintaining accurate financial records (Zakaria & Ndanyenbah, 2019).

SMEs are now a vital component of the economies of most countries, and they must take more excellent initiatives to increase their productivity and competitiveness (Ali, 2012). To stay ahead of the curve, SMEs must adapt, innovate, and deploy cutting-edge technology. The advancements in IT have produced Accounting Information Systems (AIS), which are fundamental to businesses since they provide assistance to the administration, control, integration, and coordination of their operations (Al-Okaily & Al-Okaily, 2022) and are typically computer-based systems that help with information technology and accounting activity tracking. SMEs are proposed to manage their accounting and finances effectively to provide the best out of the business, improve its profitability, and avoid disruptions. This can be achievable through adopting AIS. Firms, particularly SMEs, will perform better with a strong AIS (Ghaffar et al., 2019).

SMEs are falling behind in the digital revolution, nevertheless. Numerous investigations have been carried out to examine the connection between AIS and Manual Accounting Systems (MAS) (Opoku-Ware, 2015). There are limits to using a manual system compared to a computerised accounting system, such as a relatively weak internal control process and lower accounting information reliability. These are why companies switch from MAS to AIS, as well as factors that impact AIS and staff's ability to report their accounts properly. (Mahama and Dahlan, 2020). For small and medium-sized enterprises, using AIS is quite advantageous.

It can be seen that small and medium enterprises in Mauritius do not use AIS extensively. There are existing studies on factors influencing the adoption of AIS, but there are not enough published studies to determine their significance and impact on SMEs' intention to adopt AIS, particularly in Mauritius. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate what influences Mauritian SMEs to intend to adopt AIS and examine each factor, whether it is an important element or not that influences Mauritian SMEs in adopting AIS. Additionally, as some SMEs are still restricted in their knowledge of AIS, this research will offer a good grasp of the subject matter and its benefits.

2.1 Review of Literature

To assess the factors influencing the adoption of AIS in SMEs, we will use the TOE framework and the TAM model to get a clear view of the variables we choose and whether they positively or negatively impact the decision for SMEs to adopt AIS in their business.

The TOE Framework

The TOE framework was first proposed by Tornatzky and Fleischer in 1990. The TOE model offers a practical analytical framework for researching how various information technology innovations are adopted. TOE is a widely used theory to analyse organisational IT adoption over the last 20 years. It is beneficial in forecasting the adoption behaviour of the company when evaluating new technology (Wan Ismail & Ali, 2013). The framework breaks down the elements that influence a company's adoption of new technologies into three categories: technology, organisation (internal circumstances), and environment (external situations).

Technological Factors

The technology comprises items currently on the market that a business may utilise (Wallace et al., 2020). According to the TOE framework, technological factors are factors associated with the characteristics of the technology itself that impact its uptake and use. These factors could include the

availability of new and innovative technology, cost, complexity, compatibility, reliability, and security.

Technology adoption decisions are based on what is available and how well it integrates with the company's existing technology, according to Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990). There are many aspects of technological constructs, but our main focus would be on relative advantage as it is one of the most researched aspects of innovation regarding IT adoption at the firm level, according to Tornatzky and Klein (1982). An organisation can have advantages by implementing a specific technology over alternatives, which are referred to as relative advantages. According to Rogers (1985), it is the extent to which a technical element is thought to deliver more advantages to businesses. As Lutfi et al. 2020 point out, SMEs are primarily driven to adopt new technologies because they believe they will benefit the organisation.

The perceived benefit of using IT in the business system for SMEs has also been found by Molinillo & Japutra (2017) to be a significant predictor of adoption choice, and according to Amoako Gyampah and Salam (2004), there is a positive correlation between the relative advantage of an ERP system and its adoption. Therefore, the relative advantage encourages the dissemination of innovation for these reasons. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Relative Advantage affects the intention to adopt AIS in SMEs

Organisational Factors

The term "organisational factors" refers to any aspects of a company that might encourage its use of technology, including its size, scope of operations, and organisational structure. According to Kayer et al. (2020), the TOE framework suggests that an organisation's decision to accept technology may be influenced by its constructions, which suggests that its characteristics may impact innovation adoption.

Top management support and organisational culture are the most frequently mentioned organisational variables in AIS adoption (Ram Corkindale & Wu, 2013). According to Edison et al.

(2012), larger enterprises are more likely to implement AIS because of their complicated business processes and volume of transactions. Also, research done by Fagbemi and Olaoye (2016) found that the use of accounting information systems has a direct relationship with the size of the business in terms of capital base. Moreover, firm size and the use of computerised accounting information systems were significantly and positively associated with Gwangwava's (2012) research. The company's size provides funding for acquiring innovations and enhances the ability to spend on them. Bigger businesses are more likely than smaller businesses to be able to commit a lot of money, time, and knowledge to employ the technology.

As a result, given that prior research has shown that firm size plays a crucial role in the intention to adopt AIS and has found a positive correlation, this study aims to determine whether firm size influences the intention of Mauritius SMEs to adopt AIS. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Firm size affects the intention to adopt AIS in SMEs

Environmental Factors

Within the framework of the TOE model, the environmental construct contains the architectural business dogmatic environment, the industry, and the provider's accessibility to technology (Awa et al., 2016). External pressure dramatically impacts an organisation's decision to adopt new technology, significantly when that technology directly impacts the competition and is a strategic need (Oliveira et al., 2014). One type of external pressure is the pressure from competitors, also known as competitive pressure. According to Lutfi et al. (2020), this kind of pressure is the intensity that competing companies apply to their organisations, encouraging them to implement innovations to avoid failure and not be left behind.

Increased industry competitiveness is driving changes in the pace at which the company adopts technology to improve performance (Bhardwaj et al., 2021). According to Usman et al. (2019), SMEs are more likely to explore adopting new technology when they see that their competitors are also doing so. This is because enterprises adopting new technology do so,

believing their competitors will follow suit. Competitive pressure and ERP adoption in businesses were found to be directly correlated by Cartman and Salazar (2011). Also, according to Kurnia et al. (2015), he concluded that SMEs are more likely to embrace technology under environmental pressure.

According to Amini and Bakri (2015), increased industry competitiveness also leads to higher technology adoption rates within the company, which boosts performance and gives it a competitive edge. However, the choice to embrace enterprise resource planning is primarily taken without considering the external environmental context, according to Chau and Tam (1997). As a result, different studies have differing conclusions, and this research will determine if competitive pressure significantly impacts Mauritian SMEs' intentions to adopt AIS. It will also assist in assessing the purpose of this study. For this factor, the following hypothesis is developed:

H3: Competitive pressure affects the intention to adopt AIS in SMEs.

The TAM Model

Fred D. Davis (1989) created a framework known as the Technology Acceptance Model to forecast the adoption of new technology and examine the relationship between attitude and usage intentions. Davis (1993) established two key factors influencing users' adoption of new technologies, predicted user behaviour and showed how users begin to accept and use technology. According to TAM, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are two factors that influence a person's behaviour and intention to use technology.

Perceived Usefulness

According to Bachleda and Ouaziz (2017), perceived usefulness measures how much a person believes utilising a particular technology would boost their performance. According to Davis (1986), PU refers to a potential user's subjective likelihood that, in the context of an organisation, utilising a particular application would boost job-related productivity, performance, effectiveness, and profitability.

Perceived usefulness should be taken into account while using AIS in enterprises. Management perceives the AIS as valuable, and as performance expectations climb, so does the behavioural desire to integrate and use the system. The method might lead to an improvement in productivity and effectiveness (Tilahun, 2019).

In an empirical study, Zaini, Hamad, and Najim (2020) looked at the factors influencing the adoption of AIS in the context of Jordan. There is a correlation between the desire to adopt AIS and perceived usefulness, as indicated by the findings of a closed-ended questionnaire used to gather data from 210 enterprises in Jordan. Moreover, according to research by Mohd, Yasuo, and Nor (2012), there was a high level of AIS adoption in the three districts of Melaka, Malaysia. The study also indicated that their usefulness mostly drove the adoption of these systems. However, research by Azizah (2017) found that PU and intention to utilise AIS are not affected by its usefulness. Therefore, based on this information, the following hypothesis is developed:

H4: Perceived Usefulness affects the intention to adopt AIS in SMEs

Perceived Ease of Use

The term "perceived ease of use" describes how simple and smooth a system is to use (Davis, 1989). Measures of PEOU include convenience and how simple it is to comprehend how users interact with the system (Davis, 1989). A user's behavioural intention will probably rise if the system is easy to use and presents no obstacles.

Azmi and Sri (2015) conducted a study on the factors influencing AIS success in Indonesia and found that users of AIS will be motivated to enhance their job performance by the organisation's aim if they perceive AIS to be highly user-friendly. Also, Amin et al. (2016) discovered that the behavioural intention of workers to use AIS is proven to be strongly influenced by perceived ease of use. So, based on these studies, we can conclude that if the AIS is easy to use, the SME users would react positively to it. Therefore, the purpose of this research is to determine whether PEOU will come to the same conclusions and assist in

assessing the purpose of this study. In light of the research mentioned above, the following theory is put forth:

H5: Perceived Ease of Use affects the intention to adopt AIS by SMEs

The term perceived behavioural control (PBC) describes how easy or simple it is to carry out a particular activity or not (Lopes et al., 2019). Many aspects must be taken into account from the user's point of view to get a favourable response from the technology; otherwise, the users may react negatively or even reject the new system. According to earlier research, an individual would often embrace the AIS if they have positive behavioural control over it, and they will typically reject it if they have negative behavioural control over it.

According to Alamin et al. (2020), there is an apparent connection between technological usage and behavioural tendency regarding the general adoption of technology. Davis (1989) also determined that respondents' rejection of AIS use leads to reluctance to adopt a new system.

As a result, behavioural control is essential to adopting AIS and will be evaluated in this study to determine whether it agrees with previous studies in the Mauritian context. The following hypothesis for the above factor is therefore formulated:

H6: Perceived behavioural control affects the intention to adopt AIS by SMEs

Considering the benefits and risks when introducing the new AIS in the SME is essential, as it does not only mean installing the system and starting to use it. According to Thottoli et al. (2022), apps viewed as having a high benefit tend to be used more frequently and are favoured over competing ones in a positive use relationship. This suggests that technology is unlikely to be adopted if it is not seen to be beneficial (Mei & Aun, 2019). Therefore, the new system's advantages to SMEs will determine how eager they are to accept it. The greater the benefits, the more likely the SME will be to adopt the AIS, whereas the lower the intention to use the AIS would be if the

AIS had a significant risk. The SMEs' perceived benefits and risks and their attitudes toward them will determine whether or not they intend to adopt. In order to evaluate the purpose of this study, these two criteria will be evaluated to see whether they independently have a meaningful connection with the intention of Mauritius SMEs to adopt AIS.

The following hypotheses are formulated:

H7: Perceived Benefits affect the intention to adopt AIS by SMEs

H8: Perceived Risks affect the intention to adopt AIS by SMEs

3.1 Research Methodology

Primary data have been collected to get precise information regarding the attitudes of SME owners toward the implementation of AIS while accounting for other factors that may affect their views and which they have disclosed directly. In order to carry out this survey, a well-designed questionnaire was constructed, which consisted of a list of questions concerning my research work, which was addressed to the respondents. An online questionnaire was more practical for data collection and analysis due to the built-in tools of Google Forms, which is cost-effective as a hard copy questionnaire would be costlier and less time-consuming, where I would need to interview the owners of the SMEs one by one, which would be very time-consuming. The online questionnaires would also be beneficial regarding the accuracy of the information, as the respondents can respond in their leisure time without any pressure to respond immediately. Also, the anonymity function would enable them to respond freely about their revenue and profit numbers and give their opinions where they could not respond in a face-to-face interview.

A research population encompasses specific sets of characteristics, and in this case, they are businesses operating in any sector but not having more than 250 employees and revenue not more than MUR 100 million per year and not those who have not yet adopted AIS in their business processes.

This study used convenience sampling to randomly select nearby SMEs and deliver the questionnaire. 150 SMEs from various industries, including small and medium-sized supermarkets, pharmacies, furniture stores, and SMEs involved in construction, manufacturing, and trade, among others, responded to the approximately 280 questionnaires distributed. These SMEs were primarily contacted via email and social media by sending them Google Forms.

Before the questionnaires were distributed to the sample population for data collection, they were tested with a sample of 15 SMEs to ensure that the language was clear and that the term AIS was understandable. Before the questionnaires were distributed to the sample population for data collection, they were tested with a sample of 15 SMEs to ensure that the language was clear and that the term AIS was understandable. The study tool's internal consistency and reliability were good, as evidenced by the Cronbach Alpha Test's alpha value of 0.962, obtained after all 23 items were tested.

4.1 Results and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics

Of 150 respondents, 54% were male and 46% female, with the majority aged 18-29. Most respondents held at least a degree, suggesting a high literacy level among SME owners. Most businesses had been operational for 1 to 5 years and employed 1 to 5 people, with an average annual revenue of approximately Rs 4.8 million, classifying them primarily as microenterprises. Additionally, 46% of respondents reported numerous complex accounting transactions where implementing an AIS could be beneficial. Regarding financial feasibility, 44% believed they could afford the new system, indicating overall support for SMEs adopting AIS.

Correlation Analysis

This study used Pearson's correlation matrix to determine the relationship between seven independent factors and the dependent variable of intention to adopt AIS.

Table 1: Pearson Correlation Matrix

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Relative Advantage	Pearson Correlation	1							
Competitive Pressure	Pearson Correlation	.795**	1						
Perceived Usefulness	Pearson Correlation	.748**	.782**	1					
Perceived Ease of use	Pearson Correlation	.552**	.682**	.781**	1				
Perceived Behavioral Control	Pearson Correlation	.518**	.583**	.721**	.744**	1			
Perceived Benefits	Pearson Correlation	.652**	.774**	.784**	.766**	.729**	1		
Perceived Risks	Pearson Correlation	.512**	.551**	.596**	.489**	.383**	.602**	1	
Intention to use	Pearson Correlation	.588**	.645**	.777**	.832**	.771**	.809**	.453**	1

The variables show a positive relationship as stated from the above table: Relative Advantage and intention to use ($r = 0.588$, $P < 0.05$), Competitive Pressure and intention to use ($r = 0.645$, $P < 0.05$), Perceived Usefulness and intention to use ($r = 0.777$,

$P < 0.05$), Perceived Ease of Use and intention to use ($r = 0.832$, $P < 0.05$), Perceived Behavioral Control and intention to use ($r = 0.771$, $P < 0.05$), Perceived Benefits and intention to use ($r = 0.809$, $P < 0.05$), Perceived Risks and intention to use ($r = 0.453$, $P < 0.05$)

Intention to use AIS and Perceived Ease of use have the most substantial positive relationship. This result can be related to Azmi and Sri (2015), where it was found that users would be motivated to use AIS and react positively if they found it to be highly user-friendly and easy to use. Moreover, some variables have either a high correlation or moderate correlation in influencing the adoption of AIS, but it can be seen that Perceived Risks have the weakest correlation compared to others but still show that lower perceived risks are associated with higher intention to use AIS. Therefore, multiple linear regression analysis will be conducted as all the constructs have a positive relationship.

By calculating the linear connection between the dependent and independent variables, this approach will calculate the influence of each variable. The findings of multiple regressions employing the independent variables of Relative advantage, Firm size assessed by the approximate of assets, Competitive Pressure, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Behavioral Control, Perceived Benefits, and Perceived Risks. Moreover, the intention to use AIS as the dependent variable is shown in Tables 2,3 and 4 below.

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.894 ^a	.799	.788	.41797	2.063

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Risks, Approx Value of Assets, Perceived Behavioral Control, Relative Advantage, Perceived Ease of use, Competitive Pressure, Perceived Benefits, Perceived Usefulness

b. Dependent Variable: Intention to use

R is the correlation coefficient measuring how well the independent variables predict the dependent variable. In this case, the R-value is .849, which represents 84.9%, which is a strong positive correlation that indicates that the model has a strong relationship with the dependent variable.

R² is a statistical measure that illustrates the extent to which the independent variable may explain the variation in the dependent variable. R-squared, or the goodness of fit indicates how well the data match the regression model. Having 0.799 of R² means that there is 79.9% variation in the model, and a higher percentage would be preferred as it suggests that the model fits the data more accurately.

The Durbin-Watson statistic is a test for determining autocorrelation in the regression analysis. It will always be between 0 and 4. There is no autocorrelation when the value is DW = 2. A negative serial correlation is shown by a number more than 2,

while a positive autocorrelation is shown by a value less than 2. Therefore, in our research, it can be seen that DW is in the range of 2, so there is no autocorrelation in the residuals.

Anova Test

Table 3: Anova Table

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	98.218	8	12.277	70.277	.000 ^b
	Residual	24.633	141	.175		
	Total	122.851	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Intention to use

b. Predictors: (Constant), Approx Value of Assets (MUR), Competitive Pressure, Perceived Risks, Perceived Behavioral Control, Relative Advantage, Perceived Ease of use, Perceived Benefits, Perceived Usefulness

According to the ANOVA table above, the regression model substantially explains the variance in the dependent variable "Intention to use" depending on the given predictors. The model's high F-statistic of 70.277 suggests that it is statistically significant since it shows more variance across groups than within

groups. A lower significance level denotes a statistically significant difference between the groups. Because the significance level in this table is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, the model is statistically significant, and we may reject the null hypothesis.

Coefficients

Table 4: Coefficient

Model		Standardized	t	Sig.	Collinearity	Statistics
		Coefficients			Tolerance	VIF
	Beta					
1	(Constant)		1.461	.146		
	Relative Advantage	.096	1.427	.156	.312	3.203
	Competitive Pressure	-.180	-2.309	.022	.235	4.258
	Perceived Usefulness	.161	1.906	.059	.199	5.036
	Perceived Ease of use	.403	5.682	.000	.283	3.530
	Perceived Behavioral Control	.168	2.624	.010	.345	2.896
	Perceived Benefits	.385	4.926	.000	.232	4.305
	Perceived Risks	-.081	-1.624	.107	.567	1.763
	Approx value of assets	-.042	-1.078	.283	.932	1.074

a. Dependent Variable: Intention to use

Tolerance and VIF

They aid in evaluating the collinearity problem between the independent variables. When there is a strong correlation between two or more independent variables, this is known as collinearity. It can cause problems in regression analysis, such as making it difficult to interpret the coefficients. High tolerance indicates low multicollinearity, and low tolerance indicates high multicollinearity.

Tolerance below 0.1 can be a cause of concern, but in Table 4, we can see that all variables have a tolerance more significant than 0.1, and therefore, all variables indicate low multicollinearity.

VIF is interpreted based on the rule of thumb, which is as follows:

- 1= Not correlated
- 1-5= Moderately correlated
- >5= Highly correlated

Based on this rule of thumb, we can interpret that all variables are moderately correlated as they are all in the range of 1 to 5, suggesting that collinearity is not a significant concern in this analysis.

Relative Advantage

Table 4 shows that the beta coefficient of 0.096 suggests that relative advantage positively but weakly influences the intention to adopt AIS. The p-value is 0.156, which is 15.6%, and is not considered significant as it has exceeded 5% of the significance level. Therefore, we reject H1: Relative Advantage affects the intention to adopt AIS in SMEs, and its null hypothesis is supported.

The results above interpret that relative advantage is not a significant factor in determining the intention to adopt AIS by SMEs, which does not corroborate with the findings of Lutfi et al. (2020) where it was found that SMEs are primarily driven to adopt new technologies as they believe it will benefit the organisation and by utilising AIS would yield more benefits than not using it. However, in our study, relative advantage is not seen as a significant factor affecting the intention to adopt AIS as the SMEs may be satisfied with their existing systems, which is

enough for their needs, or they may be reluctant to take the risk to adopt AIS which could cause compatibility issues and potential risks with transitioning to a new system.

Firm Size

In this study, the value of assets determines the firm's size. This factor is not considered significant as it has a p-value of 0.283, which is 28.3%, exceeding the significance level of 5%. Therefore, we can say that we reject H2: Firm size affects the intention to adopt AIS in SMEs, and its null hypothesis is accepted. This construct also has a β value of -0.042, indicating that it does not influence the desire to adopt AIS.

The findings above demonstrated that SMEs' intention to adopt AIS is not influenced by firm size. Edison et al. (2012) results, which believed that larger companies are more likely to adopt AIS because of their complicated business processes and volume of transactions than smaller companies, conflict with our findings. Fagbemi and Olaoye (2016) discovered a strong association between AIS and company size regarding capital base, and larger organisations are more resourceful than smaller enterprises in deploying new technologies.

Since the research was conducted in Mauritius, where taxes are levied at a certain revenue threshold, our findings may differ from those of other studies conducted in other nations where the laws may differ. Because of this, SMEs in Mauritius, irrespective of the size of their business, utilise AIS to record their financial accounts accurately and to enhance their decision-making and efficiency.

Competitive Pressure

It has a p-value of 0.022, which makes it a significant factor to the dependent variable as the value is less than the significance level of 5%. However, the beta value is -0.180, a negative value indicating an inverse relationship. Therefore, since the p-value is significant, we can reject the null hypothesis. The negative beta coefficient indicates that SMEs facing higher competitive pressure are less likely to adopt AIS, and this relationship is statistically significant.

Hypothesis H3: Competitive pressure affects the intention to adopt AIS in SMEs, which is accepted as significant despite having an inverse relationship with the dependent variable. Our research does not match that of Usman et al. (2019), who stated that SMEs intend to adopt new technologies when they see their competitors doing so. It also does not match the study of Amini and Bakri (2015), who said that industry competitiveness leads to higher technology adoption rates. Our research is inverse, meaning higher competitive pressure will discourage SMEs from adopting AIS. The reasons for this could imply that SMEs may be hesitant to adopt AIS in such a competitive environment where they do not know if the system would benefit them, especially if it is new and unproven. Being under pressure would also make SMEs focus on their short-term priorities rather than investing in a new system, which could disrupt their existing workflows. This makes sense since people are less likely to utilise something if pressured.

Perceived Usefulness

The research concludes that PU is insignificant in influencing the intention to adopt AIS since the analysis generated a p-value of 0.059, which is more than the significance level of 0.05. As a result, we reject H4: Perceived Usefulness affects the intention to adopt AIS in SMEs, and its null hypothesis is supported. The β value of 0.161 suggests that PU and intention to adopt AIS by SMEs have a minor but favourable relationship.

Our research matches with Azizah (2017), who implies that attitudes toward utilising AIS are unaffected by perceived usefulness. The reasons could be a lack of skills and knowledge needed to implement and maintain the AIS, where the lack of expertise might overshadow the PU of the system. It is also seen that SMEs prefer to use a simple system that is easy to use and does not benefit them significantly. Instead, they use a complex system like AIS that could bring more benefits. Also, many SMEs have existing workflows that are seen as sufficient and do not want to disrupt them despite having more benefits.

However, our study corroborates with Zaini et al. (2020), who found a correlation between the desire to

adopt AIS, and Yasuo and Nor (2012), who said that their usefulness mainly drives the adoption of AIS.

Perceived Ease of Use

PEOU is significantly associated with SMEs' intention to adopt AIS as it has obtained a p-value of 0.000, less than 5% of the significance level. Therefore, the H5: Perceived Ease of Use affects the intention of SMEs to adopt AIS, which is accepted. PEOU also has a β value of 0.403, which shows a strong relationship that higher perceived ease of use will increase the intention to use the AIS.

The results match the study of Ami and Sri (2015), who found a positive relationship between PEOU and intention to use AIS. They concluded that users are motivated to use AIS to increase their job performance if they find the system easy to use and highly user-friendly. Also, Amin (2016) said that PEOU strongly influences workers' behavioural intention to use AIS.

Perceived Behavioral Control

This independent variable obtained a p-value of 0.010, which is less than 0.05 of significance level, which demonstrates that this variable is significant in the intention to adopt AIS. It also has a β value of 0.168, which indicates a positive relationship, suggesting that higher perceived behavioural control increases the intention to use AIS. Therefore, H6: Perceived behavioural control affects the intention to adopt AIS by SMEs is accepted, and its null hypothesis is rejected.

The results indicate that an individual's perception and behavioural control concerning AIS will determine their intention to adopt AIS or not by SMEs. The results are consistent with that of Alamin et al. (2020), who found a connection between technological usage and behavioural tendency when it comes to the adoption of technology, and according to Davis (1989), respondents' resistance to using AIS contributes to their unwillingness to embrace new systems.

Perceived Benefits

This construct obtained a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 5% and is considered significant, which means it affects SMEs'

intention to adopt AIS. It also has a beta coefficient of 0.358, indicating a strong positive relationship with using AIS. Therefore, H7: Perceived Benefits affects the intention to adopt AIS by SMEs is accepted.

Our results are consistent with those of Thottoli et al. (2020), who concluded that apps having high benefits tend to be used more frequently. If SMEs see the benefits of AIS, they will be willing to adopt the system and take advantage of it. This implies that technology is unlikely to be embraced if it is not perceived as helpful (Mei & Aun, 2019).

Perceived Risks

For this variable, the p-value is 0.107, which means it is greater than the significance level of 5%, which indicates that it is not statistically significant, and the beta coefficient is -0.081, which shows a negative association, implying that more perceived risks lead to a decrease in usage intention. Therefore, H8: Perceived Risks affect the intention to adopt AIS by SMEs is rejected as based on the facts and research presented, it can be concluded that perceived risks do not significantly impact SMEs' intentions to adopt AIS as they could believe that there are ways to reduce the dangers connected with AIS, such as vendor support, cybersecurity safeguards, and frequent upgrades.

5.1 Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

Access to accurate and meaningful information is crucial for SMEs to thrive and effectively compete in today's data-driven market. Because AIS has so many advantages, it is believed to alter how traditional accounting systems are currently used. It is said to be effective at delivering precise and quick data at a single command, enabling global data exchange, creating distinctive reporting outfits, and integrating significant risks and business processes (Choiriah & Sudibyo, 2020). Since few SMEs have said that they have used AIS in their operations, this study aimed to determine the factors affecting Mauritian SMEs' intention to adopt AIS.

This research merged the TAM model and the TOE framework. In Mauritius, it has been discovered that competitive pressure, perceived ease of use,

perceived behavioural control, and perceived benefits are important variables that influence SMEs' intentions to adopt AIS, whereby perceived ease of use was the most significant factor. This is consistent with Amin et al. (2016) and Azmi and Sri (2015), who found that workers' positive behavioural intention to use AIS is strongly influenced by perceived ease of use. In other words, users will be motivated to adopt and use the system if they find the AIS user-friendly and easy to use.

Relative Advantage, Firm Size, Perceived Usefulness, and Perceived Risks are insignificant factors in SMEs' intention to adopt AIS, whereby firm size was found to be the least significant factor to affect the dependent variable. It was discussed that SMEs in Mauritius, regardless of the size of their business, are inclined to implement AIS if they believe it will benefit them, and this was confirmed by evaluating the value of assets, where it was found that a firm having assets valued at Rs50000 is using AIS. Accordingly, only half of the suggested criteria were found to substantially affect adoption, while the other half failed to meet the study's goal of identifying the factors influencing AIS adoption by SMEs in Mauritius.

Recommendations

SME Mauritius and the Economic Development Board can take the lead in offering training and information about the advantages of AIS. An efficient training program would enable them to perceive the system as user-friendly, which would positively impact perceived ease of use, which is the factor that most strongly influences SMEs' adoption of AIS in our study. To inform SMEs of the advantages of AIS and boost interest in using the system in Mauritius, they might host workshops, seminars, and awareness campaigns. The government may also offer grant programs, tax exemptions, or subsidised AIS systems to encourage SMEs to embrace AIS. An SME must choose a reputed AIS vendor that provides customer support and after-sales services. Clear service level agreements may be established to guarantee prompt maintenance and support. It is crucial to keep lines of communication open with the vendor to receive continuous assistance to prevent mishaps when using the system. With AIS's help, SMEs may overcome

obstacles and improve their company performance and financial management.

Limitations and Further Research

Convenience sampling was the method employed to gather data for the present study. Because most of the sample size is composed of individuals between 18 and 29, and only 150 out of the 124,000 SMEs in Mauritius completed the survey, the results cannot be broadly applied. Since AIS is still relatively new and likely still developing for SMEs in Mauritius, more research is required to determine what influences SMEs to adopt the system and raise awareness of it, as the research model only accounts for half of the variance in the dependent variable.

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